

Chemistry of Benzoquinolines: Part IV

Spectroscopic Studies on 6,7-Benzoquinoline Derivatives

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Infrared and ultraviolet spectra of 6,7-benzoquinoline derivatives have been studied. Phenanthrene type of structure contains two adjacent hydrogen atoms, which are observed in infrared spectra in the region of 800 cm^{-1} and 812 cm^{-1} , while anthracene type does not. Absence of these bands in the compounds studied may be taken as a proof of their linear structure. In these compounds ultraviolet absorption increases with increasing wave-length, which also supports the linear structure of these compounds, because in anthracene the ultraviolet absorption increases with increasing wave-length, while in phenanthrene and its derivative it decreases with increasing wave-length.

IN 1885 Reed reported that a benzoquinoline derivative $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}$ (m.p. 126° - 27°) was obtained by Doebner von Miller reaction from paraldehyde, acetone and 2-naphthylamine. This base is known as Reed's base¹. On the other hand, in 1888 Combes' reported that the reaction between 2-naphthylamine and acetylacetone gave a base, known as Combes' base², (m.p. 66° - 67°). Johnson and Mathews³ found that the U.V. absorption spectra of Reed's base resembled exceedingly well with that of phenanthrene, and of Combes' base with that of anthracene. Therefore, they suggested angular structure to Reed's base (Fig. 1) and linear structure to the Combes' base (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Reed's base.

Fig. 2. Combes' base.

We have carried extensive studies on Combes' base and conclusively proved that this base is a linear compound. The present paper deals with infrared and ultraviolet spectra of some of the derivatives of Combes' base wherein it has been shown that the I.R. and U.V. data could be first fully utilized in assigning the linear or angular fusion of the aromatic rings.

Experimental

All chemicals used were chemically pure. The compounds 2-Methyl-4-styryl-6,7-benzoquinoline (I), 2-Methyl-4-carboxyl-6,7-benzoquinoline (II), 2,4-Distyryl-6,7-benzoquinoline (III), 2,4-Dicarboxyl-6,7-benzoquinoline (IV), 1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2,4-dimethyl

N-benzoyl-6,7-benzoquinoline (V) were prepared by the methods described in the literature⁴⁻⁶.

Infrared Spectra: The infrared spectra of these compounds were recorded at the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow using KBr pellets. The infrared data are given in Table I.

TABLE I—IMPORTANT INFRARED BANDS OF THE COMPOUNDS (IN CM^{-1})

Compound I	Compound II	Compound III	Compound IV	Compound V	Assignment
-	3400 b	-	3460	-	ν OH
-	1655 s	-	1700 s	1689 s	ν C=O
1496	-	1450	1450	1438	
1375 m	1385 m	-	-	1379 m	ν CH ₃
883 s	903 m	-	-	880 m	ν C-H out of plane vibration.
870 m	895 m	870 mb	870	862 w	
844 s	882 s	-	833	850 w 818 w 802 m	
835 w	835 m	-	-	-	
758 m	786 s	780 vw	785 vw	-	
748 s	755 s	755 s	750 m	750 m	
715 w	738 m	745 s	740 b	720 s	
695 s	-	695 s	-	710 m	

Discussion of the results: The infrared data of these compounds are given in Table I. A perusal of these data confirm the presence of carboxylic group in compounds II and IV. The ν OH is observed in the range of 3400 - 3460 cm^{-1} and ν C=O is observed in the range⁷ of 1655 - 1700 cm^{-1} which are characteristic of a carboxylic group. Compounds I, III and V do not show these i.r. bands.

Chemical evidences suggest that these compounds have linear structure like anthracene. This is supported by the diagnostic spectroscopic properties of these compounds. One of the fundamental differences between anthracene and phenanthrene type structures of these compounds is that while the phenanthrene type of structure contains four adjacent hydrogen atoms, two adjacent hydrogen atoms and one isolated hydrogen atom in the rings, on the other hand, anthracene type of linear structure contains four adjacent hydrogen atoms, three isolated hydrogen atoms but there is no two adjacent hydrogen atoms in the rings (Fig. 1 and 2). In phenanthrene and anthracene derivatives, the out of plane C-H vibrations are observed at characteristic positions⁸, which is shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—CHARACTERISTIC POSITIONS OF C-H OUT OF PLANE VIBRATIONS IN ANTHRACENE AND PHENANTHRENE DERIVATIVES (CM⁻¹)

Compound	Band position of 4 adjacent H-atoms	Band position of 2 adjacent H-atoms	Band position of isolated H-atoms
2-Isopropyl-phenanthrene	760 s	800 s, 812 s	890 m
2-Aminoanthraquinone	718, 726 doublet medium	846 & 855 weak doublet	886 w

The Table 2 shows that the positions and the intensity of the C-H out of plane bands can be used to distinguish between phenanthrene and anthracene derivatives. If the infrared spectra of compound I to V are examined, it is found that there is a clear doublet (710, 720) in the spectrum of compound (V). In the spectrum of compound (I) the band is present at 715 cm⁻¹, which is weak and broad but unresolved. There are very weak absorptions in this region in these compounds indicating the presence of four adjacent hydrogen atoms. The strong bands in 710–748 cm⁻¹ region may also be due to the presence of four adjacent hydrogen atoms in the compound. Orr and Thompson⁹ have traced a strong band near 750 ± 10 cm⁻¹ in considerable number of carcinogenic hydrocarbons, which contain 1,2-disubstituted polynuclear structures. Cannon and Sutherland¹⁰ identify bands at 750 cm⁻¹ in 9,10-dihydroanthracene and at 725 cm⁻¹ in anthracene itself as being due to vibrations of four adjacent hydrogen atoms. Significantly, there is no strong band in the spectra of compounds I to IV in 800–900 cm⁻¹ region. If these compounds had phenanthrene type of structures (Fig. 1) two adjacent hydrogen atoms will be present and strong bands at 800 cm⁻¹ and 812 cm⁻¹ are expected. Absence of these bands may be taken as a proof for the anthracene type of structure of these compounds.

The weaker to medium band at 870 cm⁻¹ may be due to isolated H-atoms out of plane C-H vibration. These observations are in good agreement with the anthracene type of structure of the present compounds I to IV.

Another feature of the spectra of these compounds is the presence of bands in 1375–1385 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of compounds I, II and V. These bands together with bands at 1438–1496 cm⁻¹ region is a clear indication of the presence of methyl group in I, II and V. It is evident from the Table 1 that the compounds III and IV do not have band at about 1380 cm⁻¹, which clearly indicates the absence of methyl group in them.

U. V. Spectra: In anthracene and phenanthrene derivatives^{11–13} the band positions are near about the same but there is remarkable difference in the nature of absorption. In anthracene the intensity of absorption increases with increasing wave length while in phenanthrene and its derivatives, this intensity of absorption decreases with increasing wave length. From the electronic spectra of 2-methyl-4-styryl-6,7-benzoquinoline, 4-methyl-2-carboxyl-7,8-benzoquinoline and 1,3-dimethyl-5,6-benzoquinoline it may be shown that the intensity of absorption increases with increase in wavelength in case of 2-methyl-4-styryl-6,7-benzoquinoline but opposite is the fact for 4-methyl-2-carboxyl-7,8-benzoquinoline as well as 1,3-dimethyl-5,6-benzoquinoline. It is clear from the literature¹⁴ that 1,3-dimethyl-5,6-benzoquinoline has phenanthrene type of structure. Naturally we are inclined to think that 4-methyl-2-carboxyl-7,8-benzoquinoline has phenanthrene type of fusion whereas 2-methyl-4-styryl-6,7-benzoquinoline have anthracene type of fusion of rings.

All these points may be taken as good evidences in support of the linear structure of 6,7-benzoquinoline derivatives.

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References

1. J. HASTING REED, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1885, 32, 630.
2. COMBES, *Compt. Rend.*, 1888, 106, 1536.
3. JOHNSON and MATHEWS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 2109.
4. NITYANAND SINGH and A. B. LAL, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 352.
5. IDEM, *Ber.*, 1965, 98, 2427.
6. IDEM, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 792.
7. JOHN R. DYER, *Applications of Absorption Spectra of Organic Compounds*, Prentice-Hall, Inc., N.Y., 1965, p. 35.
8. NAKANISHI, *Infrared Spectroscopy*, Holden Day Inc., San Francisco, 1962, pp. 130, 206.
9. ORR and THOMPSON, *Jour. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 218.
10. CANNON and SUTHERLAND, *Spectrochim. Acta.*, 1951, 4, 373.
11. L. LANG, *Absorption Spectra*, Hungarian Academy of Science, Budapest, 1961, Vol. I, pp. 205, 219–24, 227–28.
12. IDEM, Vol. II, pp. 293, 295, 297, 299.
13. JOHN D. ROBERTS and MARJORIE C. CASERIO, *Modern Organic Chemistry*, W. A. Benjamin, Inc., 1967, pp. 537–38.
14. JOHNSON and MATHEWS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 210.